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ISSUES OF INCREASING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF INNOVATIVE ENTERPRISES

Abstract. *In modern conditions, when competition in the market has reached high levels, ensuring that the internal environment of the enterprise meets the requirements of the market becomes one of the most important factors of successful activity, requiring constant transformation. Today's engine of economic growth is innovation, applied both in production and in operation and consumption. World experience shows that the creation and introduction of innovations is not only a way to increase the competitiveness of an enterprise, but also a significant incentive for the economic development of the country. This article will address issues related to the activation of innovative activities of enterprises in order to increase their competitiveness.*

Keywords: *innovation, innovation direction, innovation system, competitiveness, market transformation.*

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INNOVATsION KORXONALARNING RAQOBATBARDOSHLAGINI OShIRISH MASALALARI

Annotatsiya. Zamonaviy sharoitda, bozorda raqobat yuqori darajaga yetganida, korxonaning ichki muhiti bozor talablariga javob berishini ta'minlash doimiy o'zgarishni talab qiladigan muvaffaqiyatli faoliyatning muhim omillaridan biriga aylanadi. Iqtisodiy o'sishning bugungi dvigateli ishlab chiqarishda ham, foydalanishda ham, iste'molda ham qo'llaniladigan innovatsiyalardir. Jahon tajribasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsiyalarni yaratish va joriy yetish nafaqat korxonaning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish usuli, balki mamlakatning iqtisodiy rivojlanishi uchun muhim rag'batdir. Ushbu maqolada korxonalarining raqobatbardoshligini oshirish maqsadida ularning innovatsion faoliyatini faollashtirish bilan bog'liq masalalar ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: innovatsiya, innovatsion korxonalar, innovatsion tizim, raqobatbardoshlik, bozorni o'zgartirish.

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ВОПРОСЫ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ПРЕДПРИЯТИЙ

Аннотация. В современных условиях, когда конкуренция на рынке достигла высоких уровней, обеспечение соответствия внутренней среды предприятия требованиям рынка становится одним из самых важных факторов успешной деятельности, требующим постоянной трансформации. Сегодняшним двигателем экономического роста являются инновации, применяемые как на производстве, так и в эксплуатации и потреблении. Мировой опыт показывает, что создание и внедрение новшеств - это не только способ повышения конкурентоспособности предприятия, но и существенный стимул экономического развития страны. В данной статье будут рассмотрены вопросы, связанные с активизацией инновационной деятельности предприятий с целью повышения их конкурентоспособности.

Ключевые слова: инновации, инновационное предприятие, инновационная система, конкурентоспособность, рыночная трансформация.

Introduction

The need to increase competitiveness in the existing economic conditions naturally determines the implementation of innovations at industrial enterprises. At the same time, in order to increase the efficiency of the innovation process, the enterprise needs to assess

its readiness for its successful implementation. This assessment should determine the availability of a sufficient resource base, the favorable environmental conditions, the activity of the enterprise in the field of innovation and the ability to bring ideas to commercialization, based on the results of the assessment, an innovative strategy for the development of the enterprise is formed. The reliability of determining the degree of readiness for the implementation of the innovation process is one of the main guarantees of its successful implementation in the future, which will increase the competitiveness of the enterprise.

In the scientific community, there is a significant amount of work devoted to assessing the readiness of an enterprise to implement an innovation process, so this problem cannot be called new and completely unexplored. However, there are no generally recognized methodological approaches that allow us to jointly take into account both the readiness of the enterprise, and the opportunities provided by the external environment, and the activity of the enterprise in the implementation of innovative developments. To take into account all these factors, it is proposed to use a modified indicator of the innovative position of an industrial enterprise.

The industrial complex of the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the most important sectors of the economy, in which material products are created that are in demand by both private and corporate consumers. The importance of industry in ensuring economic growth was mentioned in the address of the President of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan.

The volume of Uzbekistan's gross domestic product (GDP) for 2022 at current prices reached 888.34 trillion soums. According to preliminary data of the Statistical Agency, in January-December 2022, enterprises of the republic produced industrial products worth 551.1 trillion. sum, the index of the physical volume of industrial production for the same period in 2021 amounted to 105.2%.

Literature analysis and the degree of development of the topic.

Issues related to innovation and competitiveness are widely considered in domestic and foreign literature.

Thus, the **foundations of the theory of competition and the formation** of competitive advantages of economic entities were laid in the works of foreign scientists A. Smith and D. Ricardo and continued in the works of A. Cournot, J.M. Clark, A. Marshall, W. Jevons, J. Robinson, F. Knight, E. Chamberlin, B. Olin, E. Heckscher, D. Keynes, R. Harrod, J. Schumpeter, F. Hayek, M. Porter and many other scientists.

The works of S.Y. Glazyev, A.A. Dynkin, A.M. Zhichkin, P.N. Zavlin, S.D. Ilyenkova, A.K. Kazantsev, N.D. Kondratiev, V.G. Medynsky, A.M. Mukhamedyarov, L.N. Ogoleva, A.G. Porshnev, A.I. Prigozhin, V.Ya. are devoted to the problem of innovative activity of enterprises. Gorfinkel, N.P. Maslennikova, V.N. Gunin, Yu.V. Yakovets, etc. Many aspects of the problem of innovation process management are considered in the works of foreign scientists: G. Ansoff, R. Zeiler, G. Mensch, N. Monchev, B. Santo, B. Twiss, M. Hucek, I. Schumpeter, R. Yang, etc.

The works of G.L. Azoev, B. Alstrand, I. Ansoff, A.P. Gradov, I.B. Gurkov, V.S. Efremov, F. Kotler, N.Y. Kruglova, M.I. Knysh, J. Lampel, G. Mintsberg, N.K. Moiseeva are devoted to the issues of competition and competitive advantages, competitiveness of

goods and enterprises. M. Porter, A.G. Tsyganov, R.A. Fatkhutdinova, etc. Appreciating the contribution of the above-mentioned scientists and the results obtained by them, it should be noted that the level of elaboration of the problem of activating innovation activity and increasing the competitiveness of industrial enterprises in relation to modern reality seems insufficient. The rapidly changing situation requires a more detailed study of the topic under consideration, the search for new approaches and methods.

The object of research is enterprises and processes of their dynamically sustainable development.

The theoretical basis of the research was the general traditional and modern theoretical and methodological provisions of macro- and microeconomics, new institutional economic theory, branch economics, theory and methodology of strategic management and planning, theory and methodology of investment.

The methodological basis of the research is systematic, interdisciplinary and synergetic approaches based on the integrated and integrated use of both general and special research methods. The group of general scientific research methods is formed by methods of analysis, synthesis, systematization, structuring, induction, deduction, comparative, statistical and dynamic analysis.

The information base is represented by up-to-date statistical and analytical data of the Statistical Agency under the President of Uzbekistan, data published by the Ministry of Economy and Finance. Internet resources, as well as expert opinions in the field of intensification of innovative processes in the field of industrial production.

Analysis and results.

It is proposed to systematize all the variety of interpretations of the concept of enterprise competitiveness in the context of five main campaigns. The key characteristic of the concept under study and the main criterion of the classification developed by the author is the sphere of manifestation of the competitiveness of an industrial enterprise.

Many researchers, in our opinion, rightly point out that it is unacceptable to reduce the competitiveness of an economic entity to the competitiveness of its products, and consider it from the point of view of the effectiveness of the company's activities, the business model chosen by its management, the ability to successfully compete with other market participants and expand its market share. In our opinion, the competitiveness of an industrial enterprise is the ability to conduct economically efficient activities in conditions of limited economic resources, achieved through the use of modern innovation-oriented development technologies that take into account both internal sources of competitiveness of the enterprise and external factors characterizing the situation on the market or in the industry in which the company operates. The difference of the proposed definition from the known ones (D. Voronov, P. Zabelin, V. Krivorotov, M. Kostin et al.) is a priority that is given to taking into account the use of innovation-oriented technologies for the development of the enterprise. The basis of successful competition is currently the ideas of innovative and strategic management, implemented through quality improvement, market differentiation, and production diversification.

Of fundamental importance is the formation of conditions for optimizing resource management (improvement of the material and technical base, staff training, etc.) on the

basis of strategic planning and continuous improvement of processes through the introduction of innovation-oriented technologies.

In order to identify existing problems and develop directions for enhancing innovation and increasing the competitiveness of industrial enterprises, an analysis of the current state of this sphere was carried out, on the basis of which the following trends were identified:

1) Uzbekistan has a substantial human resource reserve, which can serve as a basis for building a knowledge-based economy. At the same time, the share of higher education institutions performing research and development remains extremely low in the structure of domestic science (about 4-5% of science costs compared to 28% in the EU countries and 18-19% in Japan and the USA). Scientific activity is carried out today only in 40% of Russian universities. This trend can lead to irreversible consequences, both for science itself and for the training of qualified specialists.

2) the increase in spending on science and research in recent years.

3) insufficient innovation activity, characterized by a low level of knowledge intensity of products produced in industry, which is extremely unsatisfactory against the background of foreign countries. The composition of innovatively active organizations for the most part remains constant: more than 70% of organizations planning technological innovations in the near future have implemented them in previous years. In the industry as a whole, only 5% of organizations are independently engaged in research and development.

4) the predominance of inventions aimed at maintaining or slightly improving existing types of equipment and technologies.

The results of the study showed that funds are spent mainly on the gradual improvement of the existing product.

5) inefficient innovation infrastructure. It is the interaction and consideration of the interests of all participants in innovation activities that will allow us to work harmoniously and effectively to achieve our goals, including the goals of activating innovation and increasing the competitiveness of enterprises. The analysis of the relevant environment of enterprises allowed us to conclude that most factors have a generally insignificant impact, the overall assessment of the factors of the relevant environment is far from optimistic.

6) increase in the number of patent applications.

In 2021, the growth trend of applications for intellectual property objects to the Agency for Intellectual Activity continued, the total number of which amounted to 12248 applications, which is the highest figure in 29 years. Compared to 2020, the volume of applications submitted increased by 15.2%. The reporting year was characterized by an increase in the volume of applications for a number of intellectual property objects. The volume of applications for the grant of a patent for an invention increased by 13.1%, mainly due to the increased activity of national applicants (16%). The number of applications received for the grant of a utility model patent increased by 14.6% compared to the previous year, mainly due to the growth of applications from national applicants, which amounted to 14%. The number of applications received for the grant of a patent for an industrial design increased by 63.8% compared to the previous year due to an

increase in applications from national applicants (66.4%). The volume of applications for trademark registration increased by 29.3%, due to the increased activity of both national applicants (by 51.6%) and foreign applicants (by 15.2%). The receipt of applications for registration of computer programs and databases exceeded the level of 2020 by 73.95%. For the remaining intellectual property objects, there was a decrease in the number of applications received. The examination of intellectual property objects is carried out by the expert staff of three departments (the department of inventions and utility models, the Department of industrial designs and the department of trademarks and appellations of origin of goods). In the reporting year, a formal examination was carried out on 11982 intellectual property objects, which is 55% more than last year. The examination, in essence, was carried out on 7249 objects, which is slightly higher (2.12%) than last year. 9984 objects of intellectual property are registered in the State Registers of intellectual Property objects, which is 127.7% more than the same indicator in 2020. Legal protection has been granted to 2,569 trademarks under the Protocol to the Madrid Agreement. The total number of applications for patents for inventions received in the reporting year amounted to 665 applications, which is 13.1% more than in 2020. 413 applications or 62.1% of the total number of applications received were received from national applicants. Foreign applicants filed 252 applications or 37.9% of the total number of applications, of which the predominant number (89.8%) was filed in accordance with the Patent Cooperation Agreement (PCT).

Hence, it can be seen that the interest of enterprises in achieving high results of their activities causes the need to increase their competitiveness, which is the most important factor in ensuring efficiency and creating conditions for further development. The concept of enterprise competitiveness is complex and is interpreted very ambiguously. Based on the analysis, the concept of enterprise competitiveness was clarified as the ability to produce products that meet market requirements in a certain period of time, and to increase its share on the basis of internal and external competitive advantages of the enterprise formed through the activation of its innovation activities, the effective use of innovative, human and production potential.

One of the significant reasons for innovative passivity, methodological insufficiency of industrial enterprises are shortcomings in existing approaches, principles and methods for the practical use of new technologies in the process of innovation management.

Discussion.

To increase the efficiency of an enterprise's innovation activity, its activation management must be carried out on the basis of a set of scientifically sound principles and methods. In order to achieve the maximum effect of the activation of innovation activity, it is necessary to constantly develop and improve the methodological base. One of the most important components of the methodological provisions of the activation of innovation activity are the principles. The principle is understood as one of the initial, basic requirements for the process of activating innovation activity, the implementation of which ensures its effectiveness.

In order to ensure an effective process of activating innovation activity, a number of system-wide and special principles characteristic of this sphere were analyzed and justified.

Based on the analysis, a number of special principles for the activation of innovative activity of enterprises are proposed:

1. Recognition of the priority of innovative factors for improving both competitiveness and efficiency of the enterprise as a whole.

The weakest link today is not so much financing as the lack of innovation management skills. The main problem remains the severance of ties between the main participants in the innovation process, information opacity and therefore low motivation, both for the development and financing of innovations. An analysis of the problems associated with accelerating the integration of science and production, the introduction of innovative processes in industry, shows that many of them stem from the lack of a well-formed infrastructure to support horizontal links between industrial enterprises, scientific and financial organizations.

2. Legal protection of innovative ideas. The results of the innovative activity of employees are the competitive advantages of the enterprise and the task of any enterprise is to protect them. Without ensuring reliable legal protection of the results of innovative activity, the possibility of their effective use is jeopardized. 3. Information interconnection. When implementing innovative activities, intensive information flows are created that meet the needs of individual management services. An approach based on the use of an integrated information system that provides a single base for all departments of this enterprise should be incorporated into the enterprise management system.

4. Active and innovative participation of each employee in improving the efficiency of innovation and competitiveness of products.

The implementation of this principle involves the use of various methods of material and moral incentives, including: setting a high salary in advance and receiving a corresponding high quality as a result; applying bonuses and awards for high achievements in the field of increasing innovation activity; taking into account the individual potential and the real contribution of everyone to improving and ensuring the required quality of products; developing competitiveness in the work on to increase and ensure high efficiency between individual employees, divisions and enterprises.

5. Interest in the results of their work of all subjects of innovative activity. Internal motives that stimulate innovative activity are becoming more and more interesting. These include the following: the desire to really feel the results of their work, to have opportunities for creative search, to take the initiative, to feel the support of their innovative activities from the enterprise: both in the form of material and financial support for projects initiated by innovators, and in the form of social recognition of their special role in the organization.

6. State support of innovation activities. It will allow to determine the place of scientific and scientific-technical activity in the state, society, economy; the legal status of a researcher; the multiplicity of sources of financing of enterprises, the principles of scientific activity management, the main forms of influence of public authorities at

various levels in the field of science; reflect the legal basis for regulating international scientific and technical cooperation.

Activation of innovation activity must also be carried out at all stages of the life cycle of innovation activity, that is, it must permeate all its stages and include the following stages: R&D; production; sale; operation (consumption); disposal.

The implementation of activation at each stage of the innovation life cycle ensures that the control effects cover the entire complex of stages and stages of the innovation process.

Along with the principles, the effectiveness of the activation of innovation activity largely depends on the methods that will be used in its implementation. At the same time, methods are understood as methods and techniques for implementing managerial activities and influencing the personnel of an enterprise to achieve significant results when activating innovative activities.

The results of the activity of innovation activation groups largely depend on the tools used. Among them, the method of system analysis, goal structuring, expert, computational, comparisons, modeling, correlation and regression analysis, analogies, generating ideas, planning experiments, graphical modeling should be highlighted. Ultimately, the success of the activities of such groups largely depends on the mass participation of workers, which can be ensured by the systematic painstaking work of the entire management corps of the enterprise. At the same time, it is important to stimulate the work of groups "from above", directing their creative potential to solve the most important tasks to achieve the goals of the enterprise.

Conclusion.

Operations related to the evaluation in general and the evaluation of proposals and recommendations for the activation of innovation, in particular, can be combined into three typical stages: preparatory; evaluation stage and final.

The specific sequence of implementation of the methodological provisions of the assessment in most real cases depends on the purpose, qualifications of the persons conducting the development and implementation of the methodology, and the situation of assessing the level of activation of innovation activity.

The entire evaluation process should be carried out with continuous forward and backward links of each of the above operations, which should be performed, at least within each of the stages, if possible, sequentially- in parallel. The implementation of this approach makes it possible to reduce the evaluation period and achieve the goals of solving evaluation tasks in a shorter time.

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Tarqatish shakli: jurnal

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Muassis(lar)i: "AL-FERGANUS" mas'uliyati cheklangan jamiyat

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